

SOME BIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF THE JAPANESE CLOVER PLANT JAPONICA L.

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Abstract. In the article, contains information about the beneficial properties of the tricot plant for humans, its wide use in folk medicine and modern medicine. Information on some biological features of the development of the structure, flowering and ripening of fruits is given.

Keywords. Thres species, medicinal properties, decorative representatives, phenological phases, structure of vegetative and generative organs.

It has been determined that there are 10-12 thousand species of medicinal plants on earth. Currently, the chemical, pharmacological and medicinal properties of more than 1000 (50%-60%) plant species have been investigated. There are more than 700 species of medicinal plants in Uzbekistan. President Sh. According to Mirziyoyev's order of April 10, 2020 "Measures for the protection, cultivation, processing and rational use of medicinal plants growing in the wild" No. belongs to the Japanese clover plant [1].

The representatives of the sylvidosh family are widely distributed on the earth, most species are distributed mainly in the temperate countries of the Northern Hemisphere, less in the Southern Hemisphere, and in tropical regions only in mountainous areas. Most representatives are small trees and shrubs, there are very few grasses. There are 6 species of this family in the flora of Uzbekistan, and 5 of them are cultivated as ornamental plants [2,15].

Most of the plants belonging to the sylvidosh family are forest plants. They are mainly part of the shrublands, and can also be found on river banks, in the depths of steep ravines, in light places of thickets on the edges of forests [3].

There are 240 species of the Lonicera family on Earth. More than 20 species have been identified in the flora of Uzbekistan. Among them, Japanese clover (*Lonicera japonica* Thunb.) *stenantha* Pojark.), Korolkov's triple (*L. Korolkovii* Stapf.), small-flowered triple (*L. micrantha* Rgl.), small-leaved triple (*L. bracteolaris* Boiss et Buhse), small-leaved triple (*L. microphylla* Willd. ex Roem. et Schult.), Semyonov's thrips (*L. Semenovii* Rgl.), Zarafshon's thrips (*L. zeravschanica* Pojark.), gray thrips (*L. cinerea* Pojark.), Olga's thrips (*L. Olgae* Rgl. et Schmalh.), wonderful thrips (*L. paradoxa* Pojark.), different-leaved three-leaved (*L. heterophylla* Decne), imitation three-leaved (*L. simulatrix* Pojark.), different hair three-leaved (*L. heterotricha* Bond.), unequal hair three-leaved (*L. anisotricha* Bond.), Altman's tripe (*Lonicera Altmannii* Rgl.) and Ruprecht's tripe (*L. Ruprechtiana* Rgl.) [2,4].

All these species are widely used for human needs, in folk medicine and scientific medicine. People have been using the fruits of the tricot plant and many other decorative properties of its organs since BC [5].

In Chinese and Russian folk medicine, *L. caprifolium* L., *L. japonica* Thunb. and tinctures made from flowers, fruits, stems and leaves of *L. edulis* species are used in the treatment of hypertension, gastritis, anemia, wounds, viral and bacterial diseases. Extracts prepared from its leaves have been found to have detoxification properties - cleansing the skin, lymph and blood of harmful metabolic products, heavy metals and other toxins. The extract of the fruits and leaves of the tricot plant is used in cosmetics [6,7]. Saponins, tannins, and inositol (cyclohexane-1,2,3,4,5,6-hexol) substances were found in the leaves of *L. japonica* plant [17].

The concentration of vitamin C in the fruit of the tricot plant is not inferior to the amount in citrus fruits, it contains calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, potassium, iron, beta-carotene pigment with antioxidant properties, B vitamins, iodine, silicon, copper, manganese and human it has been determined that there are several other trace elements necessary for vital activity [8].

The fruits of the tricot plant have a beneficial effect on the cardiovascular system and the gastrointestinal tract, the pectins, tannins and organic acids contained in it clean the blood vessels from slags and cholesterol, thus it is important in the prevention of atherosclerosis [9].

Three fruits stimulate the immune system and increase the stimulating properties of all human organs and systems [10].

Many species of the tricot plant are widely cultivated as ornamental plants due to the attractiveness of their flowers, branches, and leaves during flowering and fruit ripening [11,12,16,18]. Therefore, these plants can be used in vertical landscaping works in Uzbekistan [13].

Monitoring results.

The study of the phenological phases of the Japanese cherry plant was carried out during the years 2020-2023 on representatives planted and grown in the conditions of the city of Termiz.

Japanese clover (*Lonicera japonica* Thunb.) is also widely cultivated in Uzbekistan as an ornamental plant. Japanese triple K. It is a plant belonging to the mesophanerophyte group according to the Raunkier system, and it is a creeping plant that grows from 2 to 6 m in height. The stem is covered with brown or reddish bark. The part of the stem up to about 1.5 m from the ground is bare, twisted, and the upper part is very branched (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. External appearance and flowering branches of *Lonicera japonica* Thunb.

The leaves are simple, sideless, opposite on the stem, the plate is ovate or oblong-ovate, the tips are sharp, the edges are entire, the base is rounded, soft hairy. The upper side of the leaf-plate is dark green, the lower side is light green, with

reticulate veins. Leaves in the lower part of the branches (4.5–6.5 cm long and 2.5–4.0 cm wide) are short banded (0.9–1.3 cm), upper leaves (1.8–2.5 cm and 1.5–2.0 cm wide) and the upper ones are 1.2–1.5 cm long and 1.0–1.5 cm wide, and these leaves are Flowers are placed at the bottom (Fig. 1).

Inflorescences of the Japanese clover plant are complex shingles. In the axils of the leaves at the tip of the branches, there are first-order lateral arrows, each of which ends with a pair of flowers, that is, two flowers are located in one common band (Fig. 1).

Artyushenko Z.T. and Fyodorov A.A. According to the terms of the Atlas [14], its frondous inflorescences are of the type of complex monopodial - complex shingle inflorescences (Figures 1-2). In this case, its inflorescences are considered to be polythelic, unrestricted dibothrium, and the flowers are located on the lateral axes of the first order.

The size of the flowers, together with the seeds, reaches 5.5–6.0 cm. They are attached to the first-order axes with the help of their short (2.5–3.0 mm long) corollas (Fig. 2). At the junction of the first order of flowers, there are small bracts, 1.5–1.7 cm long and 0.8–0.9 cm wide, which are short on the stem (0.3–0.4 cm long reaching) are combined with clauses.

Fig. 2. A - The first opening period of flowers (pollen phase of the flower), B - the seed phase of the flower.

Flowers are zygomorphic, bisexual. The calyx is 5, small, growing together, 0.2-0.3 cm long. Among the small calyxes there are 2-lipped gultojas, the tips of which are divided into 5 pieces, the upper lip is four, the lower lip is one piece. The

flowers are fragrant, especially in the evening and at night, the fragrance of the flowers intensifies (Fig. 2).

Its 3.5-3.8 cm long flowers are white at first, then turn yellow. The flowers are covered with hair on the outside, the back is slightly shorter than the tube. The size of the flutes is 2.8-3.0 cm. There are 5 pinnae (2.5–3.0 cm), they are attached to the middle part of the tubercle (Fig. 2) and are the same size as the back.

The length of the seed column is 5.3–5.5 cm, the beak is three-lobed, it is longer than the anthers (Fig. 2), and it is located much higher than them (herkogamy).

The fruit is a dark berry, 6–8 mm in size. Two berry fruits are formed in the tip of the common (one) band for two flowers (Fig. 2). Inside the fruit, small, dark-brown seeds ripen.

In Termiz conditions, the vegetation of the Japanese tricot starts from the first or second ten days of March, depending on the early or late arrival of the spring season, and lasts until the end of October, the active vegetation period of the plant is 275 ± 5 days. Japanese maple is an evergreen plant that does not shed its leaves even in winter (Fig. 3).

The budding (budonization) phase of the plant was observed in the last decade of April, the beginning of the flowering phase is in the first ten days of May, and the full flowering is in late May, early June. The fruit ripens in September-October, and its full ripening lasts until the end of November (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Phenospectra of *Lonicera japonica* Thunb. in Termiz conditions.

In conclusion, it can be said that the Japanese clover plant is fully acclimatized to the conditions of Termiz, winters well, goes through the vegetation phases, blooms and gives fruits and germinated seeds. In thermal conditions, it can fully withstand the scorching heat of summer. It can be propagated vegetatively from cuttings. Since the branches, leaves, flowers and fruits of this plant are very decorative, we recommend using them in vertical landscaping.

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